

A SINGULAR HYBRID FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS OF INTERLAMINAR CRACK PROBLEMS

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SUMMARY: Singular stress distributions near interlaminar crack in composite laminate under various loadings are analyzed by a singular hybrid element method which is developed based on the elasticity solutions and the variational principle of a hybrid functional. Asymptotic solutions for displacements and stresses near the interfacial crack between dissimilar anisotropic materials are utilized as the displacement and stress expressions within the crack element. The singular hybrid element is used in conjunction with the conventional displacement-based, quasi three-dimensional elements to study the detailed nature of the displacements and stresses in vicinity of the interlaminar crack tip.

Analyzing a small interfacial crack in a large composite under mechanical loading, we demonstrate that the present numerical solutions are in good agreement with the analytical ones for a interfacial crack in infinite composite. Then, we apply the present method for analysis of delamination cracks originating from transverse cracking in composite under various loadings. Comparisons of the present solutions with the results by the displacement finite element method show the accuracy and efficiency of the present finite element procedure.

KEYWORDS: delamination, stress singularity, potential energy release rate, finite element method, singular element, hybrid element, variational principle

INTRODUCTION

Delamination is the most commonly observed failure mode in composite laminates under mechanical and hygrothermal loadings which have been extensively utilized for the lightweight structures. Onset and growth of the delamination can be characterized by the fracture mechanics based on the singular stress distributions at the crack tip. The stress field near the interfacial crack can be analyzed by the conventional displacement finite element method [1, 2] or the singular hybrid finite element method [3, 4].

In this paper, a singular hybrid element method for studying the stresses near the interfacial crack is presented. The fundamental solution for the displacements and stresses in vicinity of the crack tip is reviewed first. The singular crack element is formulated based on the elasticity solutions and a hybrid variational principle. Comparisons of the present numerical

solutions with the analytical ones or the numerical ones by the displacement finite element method demonstrate the accuracy and efficiency of the present finite element method.

ASYMPTOTIC SOLUTION FOR DISPLACEMENTS AND STRESSES NEAR INTERFACIAL CRACK TIP

For the generalized plane strain state, displacements are given by

$$u_i = U_i(x_1, x_2) = U_i(x_\sigma) \quad (1)$$

We use the convention that all Latin indices take the values 1, 2, 3 and all Greek indices the values 1, 2.

Two-Dimensional Anisotropic Elasticity Problem

The equilibrium equations are

$$\sigma_{i\sigma, \sigma} = 0 \quad (2)$$

The strain-displacement relations are

$$\varepsilon_{k\ell} = \frac{1}{2}(u_{k, \ell} + u_{\ell, k}) \quad (3)$$

The constitutive equations are

$$\sigma_{i\sigma} = C_{i\sigma k\ell} \varepsilon_{k\ell} \quad (4)$$

Substituting Eqns 3 to Eqns 4 and to Eqns 2, we have

$$C_{i\sigma k\ell} u_{k, \sigma\ell} = C_{i\sigma k\rho} u_{k, \sigma\rho} = 0 \quad (5)$$

It can be assumed [5] that general solutions to Eqns 5 are given by

$$u_k = a_k f(z) \quad z = x_1 + p x_2 \quad (6)$$

where a_k and p are, respectively, the eigenvector and eigenvalue to be determined.

Inserting Eqns 6 into Eqns 5, we get

$$\{C_{i1k1} + p(C_{i1k2} + C_{i2k1}) + p^2 C_{i2k2}\} a_k f(z)_{,zz} = 0 \quad (7)$$

The condition that all a_k 's are not zero gives six eigenvalues and the associated eigenvectors, and

$$p_\alpha, p_{\alpha+3} = \bar{p}_\alpha \quad ; \quad \mathbf{a}_\alpha, \mathbf{a}_{\alpha+3} = \bar{\mathbf{a}}_\alpha \quad (\text{Im}[p_\alpha] > 0, \alpha = 1, 2, 3)$$

where Im stands for the imaginary part and the overbar denotes the complex conjugate. The displacements are expressed as

$$\mathbf{u} = \sum_{\alpha=1}^3 \{ \mathbf{a}_\alpha f_\alpha(z_\alpha) + \bar{\mathbf{a}}_\alpha f_{\alpha+3}(\bar{z}_\alpha) \} \quad z_\alpha = x_1 + p_\alpha x_2 \quad (8)$$

And the stresses take the form

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \sigma_{i1} &= - \sum_{\alpha=1}^3 \left\{ p_{\alpha} b_{i\alpha} \frac{d}{dz_{\alpha}} f_{\alpha}(z_{\alpha}) + \bar{p}_{\alpha} \bar{b}_{i\alpha} \frac{d}{d\bar{z}_{\alpha}} f_{\alpha+3}(\bar{z}_{\alpha}) \right\} \\ \sigma_{i2} &= \sum_{\alpha=1}^3 \left\{ b_{i\alpha} \frac{d}{dz_{\alpha}} f_{\alpha}(z_{\alpha}) + \bar{b}_{i\alpha} \frac{d}{d\bar{z}_{\alpha}} f_{\alpha+3}(\bar{z}_{\alpha}) \right\} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (9)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} b_{i\alpha} &= (C_{k1i2} + p_{\alpha} C_{i2k2}) a_{i\alpha} \\ &= -\frac{1}{b_{\alpha}} (C_{i1k1} + p_{\alpha} C_{i1k2}) a_{i\alpha} \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

Displacements and Stresses near Interfacial Crack Tip

If we assume a power-type eigenfunction for $f(z)$ in Eqns 6 as

$$f(z) = \frac{cz^{\delta+1}}{\delta+1} \quad \text{Re}[\delta] > -1 \quad (11)$$

near the crack tip shown in Fig.1, we have

$$f_{\alpha} = q_{\alpha} f(z_{\alpha}) \quad f_{\alpha+3}(\bar{z}_{\alpha}) = h_{\alpha} f(\bar{z}_{\alpha}) \quad (\alpha = 1, 2, 3) \quad (12)$$

From the stress conditions on the crack surface and the continuity conditions for displacements and tractions on the interface, we get

$$\begin{aligned} \delta_n^I &= -\frac{1}{2} + n + i\gamma & \bar{\delta}_n^I &= -\frac{1}{2} + n - i\gamma & \delta_n^R &= -\frac{1}{2} + n & \delta_n^{N_1} &= \delta_n^{N_2} = \delta_n^{N_3} = n \\ & & & & & & & (n = 0, 1, 2, \dots) \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

It follows from Eqns 8, 9, 11 and 12 that the displacements and stresses are given by

$$u_i^{(k)} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \left[s_n^{I_1} \text{Re}[\varphi_{in}^{I(k)}] + s_n^{I_2} \text{Im}[\varphi_{in}^{I(k)}] + s_n^R \text{Re}[\varphi_{in}^{R(k)}] + \sum_{j=1}^3 s_n^{N_j} \text{Re}[\varphi_{in}^{N_j(k)}] \right] \quad (k = 1, 2) \quad (14)$$

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \sigma_{i1}^{(k)} &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \left[s_n^{I_1} \text{Re}[X_{in}^{I(k)}] + s_n^{I_2} \text{Im}[X_{in}^{I(k)}] + s_n^R \text{Re}[X_{in}^{R(k)}] + \sum_{j=1}^3 s_n^{N_j} \text{Re}[X_{in}^{N_j(k)}] \right] \\ \sigma_{i2}^{(k)} &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \left[s_n^{I_1} \text{Re}[\psi_{in}^{I(k)}] + s_n^{I_2} \text{Im}[\psi_{in}^{I(k)}] + s_n^R \text{Re}[\psi_{in}^{R(k)}] + \sum_{j=1}^3 s_n^{N_j} \text{Re}[\psi_{in}^{N_j(k)}] \right] \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (15)$$

HYBRID FINITE ELEMENT FORMULATION

The functional of the hybrid Hellinger-Reissner principle [6] is given by

$$\Pi_{Rh} = \sum_m \left[\iint_{A_m} \left\{ \frac{1}{2} \sigma_{ij} (u_{i,j} + u_{j,i}) - U_c(\sigma_{ij}) \right\} dA - \int_{S_m} T_i (u_i - \tilde{u}_i) ds - \int_{(S_u)_m} T_i (u_i - \bar{u}_i) ds - \int_{(S_\sigma)_m} \bar{T}_i u_i ds \right] \quad (16)$$

where A_m is the area of element ; S_m is the interelement boundary, $(S_u)_m$ the boundary where displacements are prescribed, $(S_\sigma)_m$ the boundary where tractions are prescribed ; and \tilde{u}_i is displacements defined along the element boundary. If we assume that

$$\tilde{u}_i = \bar{u}_i \quad \text{on } (S_u)_m \quad (17)$$

$$u_i = \tilde{u}_i \quad \text{on } (S_\sigma)_m \quad (18)$$

and introduce Eqns 18 into Eqn 16 by adding the term

$$- \int_{(S_\sigma)_m} T_i (u_i - \tilde{u}_i) ds$$

we obtain a functional of a modified hybrid Hellinger-Reissner principle as

$$\Pi_{mRh} = \sum_m \left[\iint_{A_m} \left\{ \frac{1}{2} \sigma_{ij} (u_{i,j} + u_{j,i}) - U_c(\sigma_{ij}) \right\} dA - \int_{\partial A_m} T_i (u_i - \tilde{u}_i) ds - \int_{(S_\sigma)_m} \bar{T}_i \tilde{u}_i ds \right] \quad (19)$$

where ∂A_m is the boundary of A_m .

If the stresses satisfy the equilibrium equations and the compatibility conditions, Eqn 19 becomes

$$\begin{aligned} \Pi_{mRh} &= \sum_m \left[\iint_{A_m} \frac{1}{2} \sigma_{ij} u_{i,j} dA - \int_{\partial A_m} T_i (u_i - \tilde{u}_i) ds - \int_{(S_\sigma)_m} \bar{T}_i \tilde{u}_i ds \right] \\ &= \sum_m \left[\int_{\partial A_m} T_i \tilde{u}_i ds - \frac{1}{2} \int_{\partial A_m} T_i u_i ds - \int_{(S_\sigma)_m} \bar{T}_i \tilde{u}_i ds \right] \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

And, if the stress boundary conditions

$$\bar{T}_i = 0 \quad \text{on } (S_\sigma)_m \quad (21)$$

are satisfied, Eqn 20 takes the form

$$\begin{aligned} \Pi_{mRh} &= \sum_m \left[\int_{\partial A_m} T_i \tilde{u}_i ds - \frac{1}{2} \int_{\partial A_m} T_i u_i ds \right] \\ &= \sum_m \left[\int_{\partial A_m} \mathbf{T}^T \tilde{\mathbf{u}} ds - \frac{1}{2} \int_{\partial A_m} \mathbf{T}^T \mathbf{u} ds \right] \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

Stiffness Matrix Formulation for Singular Crack Element

If we truncate the series expansion in Eqns 14 and 15 at $n = N$, we have the displacements and tractions at the interelement boundary of A_m as

$$\mathbf{u} = \mathbf{U}\boldsymbol{\beta} \quad \mathbf{T} = \mathbf{R}\boldsymbol{\beta} \quad (23)$$

where

$$\boldsymbol{\beta} = [s_0^{I_1}, s_0^{I_2}, s_0^R, s_0^{N_1}, s_0^{N_2}, s_0^{N_3}; \dots; s_N^{I_1}, s_N^{I_2}, s_N^R, s_N^{N_1}, s_N^{N_2}, s_N^{N_3}] \quad (24)$$

The interelement boundary displacements are expressed in terms of the nodal displacements \mathbf{q} as

$$\tilde{\mathbf{u}} = \mathbf{L}\mathbf{q} \quad (25)$$

Substituting Eqns 23 and 25 into Eqn 22, we get

$$\begin{aligned} \Pi_{mRh}^{(m)} &= \boldsymbol{\beta}^T \left[\int_{\partial A_m} \mathbf{R}^T \mathbf{L} ds \right] \mathbf{q} - \frac{1}{2} \boldsymbol{\beta}^T \left[\int_{\partial A_m} \mathbf{R}^T \mathbf{U} ds \right] \boldsymbol{\beta} \\ &= \boldsymbol{\beta}^T \left[\int_{\partial A_m} \mathbf{R}^T \mathbf{L} ds \right] \mathbf{q} - \frac{1}{2} \boldsymbol{\beta}^T \left[\frac{1}{2} \int_{\partial A_m} (\mathbf{R}^T \mathbf{U} + \mathbf{U}^T \mathbf{R}) ds \right] \boldsymbol{\beta} \\ &= \boldsymbol{\beta}^T \mathbf{G} \mathbf{q} - \frac{1}{2} \boldsymbol{\beta}^T \mathbf{H} \boldsymbol{\beta} \end{aligned} \quad (26)$$

where

$$\mathbf{G} = \int_{\partial A_m} \mathbf{R}^T \mathbf{L} ds \quad H = \frac{1}{2} \int_{\partial A_m} (\mathbf{R}^T \mathbf{U} + \mathbf{U}^T \mathbf{R}) ds \quad (27)$$

Taking variation of $\Pi_{mRh}^{(m)}$, we obtain

$$\delta \Pi_{mRh}^{(m)} = \delta \boldsymbol{\beta}^T (\mathbf{G} \mathbf{q} - \mathbf{H} \boldsymbol{\beta}) = 0 \quad (28)$$

which gives

$$\boldsymbol{\beta} = \mathbf{H}^{-1} \mathbf{G} \mathbf{q} \quad (29)$$

Substituting Eqns 29 into Eqn 26, the variational functional is expressed as

$$\Pi_{mRh}^{(m)} = \frac{1}{2} \mathbf{q}^T [\mathbf{G}^T \mathbf{H}^{-1} \mathbf{G}] \mathbf{q} = \frac{1}{2} \mathbf{q}^T \mathbf{k}_s \mathbf{q} \quad (30)$$

where \mathbf{k}_s is the stiffness matrix for the hybrid singular crack tip element.

In the present finite element approach, a 17-node, hybrid crack element shown in Fig.2 with 51 degrees of freedom is constructed. The total number N of terms in the truncated series in Eqn 23 is takes as 14. Standard quadratic interpolation functions are used for the L in Eqns 25 to ensure matching of the boundary displacements of the singular hybrid element with those of adjacent 8-node, 24 degrees of freedom, isoparametric regular elements as shown in Fig.3.

NUMERICAL RESULTS

To confirm the singular hybrid finite element solutions, we analyze a large carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) $[0^\circ/90^\circ]$ laminate with a small central crack of length $2a$ subjected to the uniform far field stress σ_{22}^∞ as shown in Fig.4. The total and singular stress distributions along the interface are shown in Fig.5. The singular stress distributions are shown in Fig.6 together with those obtained by the analytical solution for an infinite plate [7]. Comparison of the numerical solution for the interlaminar singular stresses with the analytical one is also shown in Table 1. The potential energy release rates from the two approaches are

A large CFRP $[\theta^\circ/-\theta^\circ]$ laminate with a small central crack is also analyzed. The numerical solution for the potential energy release rates is shown in Fig.7 together with the analytical one [7].

Then, we analyze CFRP laminate with delamination originating from transverse cracking as illustrated in Fig.8. The stress distributions along the interface of CFRP laminate under tensile strain ε_{11}^∞ are shown in Fig.9 together with those obtained by the displacement finite element method [2] with fine discretization as illustrated in Fig.10.

CONCLUSIONS

A singular hybrid interfacial crack element has been developed to study the stresses near interfacial crack combining with the conventional regular elements. The present numerical solutions for a small interfacial crack in a large composite are in good agreement with the analytical ones for a crack in an infinite composite. And comparison of the present solutions for delamination originating from transverse cracking with those by the conventional displacement-based finite element method show the accuracy and efficiency of the present finite element procedure.

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Table 1 : Interlaminar singular stresses near crack tip of CFRP [0°/90°] laminate under σ_{22}^{∞} ($x_2=0, r=x_1-a$).

r/a	Analytical Solution		FEM Solution	
	$\sigma_{22} / \sigma_{22}^{\infty}$	$\sigma_{21} / \sigma_{22}^{\infty}$	$\sigma_{22} / \sigma_{22}^{\infty}$	$\sigma_{21} / \sigma_{22}^{\infty}$
0.0001	65.35043	-33.60590	64.43491	-33.12293
0.0002	46.88079	-21.78091	46.22377	-21.46717
0.0005	30.15390	-12.09209	29.73109	-11.91726
0.001	21.56054	-7.63736	21.25812	-7.52654
0.002	15.39514	-4.74804	15.17912	-4.67883
0.005	9.84300	-2.45179	9.70482	-2.41575
0.01	7.00676	-1.43630	6.90836	-1.41499
0.05	3.16682	-0.33072	3.12232	-0.32557
0.1	2.24477	-0.13838	2.21321	-0.13608
0.5	1.00473	0.03755	0.99059	0.03709
1.0	0.70922	0.05672	0.69924	0.05603

Fig. 1 : Semi-infinite crack.

Fig. 2 : Hybrid singular crack element.

Fig. 3 : Finite element discretization.

Fig. 4 : CFRP[0°/90°] laminate with central crack of length $2a$ under σ_{22}^∞ .

Fig. 5 : Stress distributions along interface near crack tip of CFRP [0°/90°] laminate under σ_{22}^∞ ($x_2 = 0$, $r = x_1 - a$).

Fig. 6 : Singular stress distributions along interface near crack tip of CFRP [0°/90°] laminate under σ_{22}^∞ ($x_2 = 0$, $r = x_1 - a$).

Fig. 7 : Potential energy release rates for crack of CFRP $[\theta^\circ/\theta^\circ]$ laminate under σ_{22}^∞ .

Fig. 8 : CFRP $[0^\circ/90^\circ]_s$ laminate with delamination originating from transverse crack tip.

Fig. 9 : Stress distributions along interface of CFRP $[0^\circ/90^\circ]_s$ laminate with delamination originating from transverse crack tip.

Fig. 10 : Discretization for displacement finite element analysis of CFRP $[0^\circ/90^\circ]_s$ laminate with delamination originating from transverse crack tip.